

Expanding an Ontology with Semantically Linked CFD-Simulation Data by Segmentation into Reusable Concepts

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CFD - Ontology for Catalysis

- Aligning data structures (knowledge graphs)
- Expandable (terms/classes, relations/axioms, information/definitions, ...)
- Interconnectivity (e.g. SQL database, metadata frameworks, electronic laboratory notebooks,...)

Storage and Metadata Annotation

```

Microreactor has Y-mixing-element
"Flow Analysis 1": {
  "ANALYSIS TYPE": {...},
  "DOMAIN": {
    "Default Domain": { ...
    "BOUNDARY": {
      "Default Domain Default": { ...
      "BOUNDARY CONDITIONS": {...}},
    "DOMAIN MODELS": {...}},
  }
}
    
```

New Simulations / Change Parameters

Infer Knowledge

↑ Eddies & ↓ Reaction → unmixed Pockets

Motivation – Data Origin

- Data availability
 - Experimental [1]
 - Theoretical [2]
 - Computational fluid dynamics (CFD)
 - Micro reactor of Little Things Factory
- Data from master thesis at TU Dortmund University
 - Subdivision of simulations
 - Variety of settings

[1] Frede, Timothy Aljoscha; Burke, Inga; Kockmann, Norbert (2021)

[2] Frede, Timothy Aljoscha; Dietz, Marlene; Kockmann, Norbert (2021)

Ontologies – A simple example

- Information is stored in triplets

- Reasoning enhances data

- „The reaction in reactor X148A uses iron catalysts“
- Inference yields: „The reaction in reactor X148A is a Haber-Bosch reaction which in turn is a catalytic reaction and uses iron catalyst as catalyst.“

Motivation – Data Structure

Not FAIR-data but FAIR-storage

- Findable:
Queryable / SPARQL
- Accessible:
Classification via metadata / OWL & SHACL
- Interoperable:
Non-proprietary file formats / RDF
- Reusable
Connection to database and maintaining of metadata / SPARQL & RDF

Process Steps

- Summary file as data source
 - Unknown structure
 - Complex syntax
- JSON-archive
 - Human-readable
 - Machine-searchable


```

"FLOW": {
  "Flow Analysis 1": {
    "ANALYSIS TYPE": {
      "Option": "Steady State",
      "EXTERNAL SOLVER COUPLING": {
        "Option": "None"}},
    "DOMAIN": {
      "Default Domain": {
        "Coord Frame": "Coord 0",
        "Domain Type": "Fluid",
        "Location": "B3105",
        "BOUNDARY": {
          "Default Domain Default": {
            "Boundary Type": "WALL",
            "Location": "F2988.3105",
            "Use Profile Data": "False",
            "BOUNDARY CONDITIONS": {
              "MASS AND MOMENTUM": {
                "Option": "No Slip Wall"}}}}},
        "DOMAIN MODELS": {
          "BUOYANCY MODEL": {
            "Option": "Non Buoyant"}},
        ...
  }
}
  
```

Ontology

- VIMMP [1]
 - Domain / task
 - ✗ Inconsistent

- EMMO [2]
 - Material modeling
 - Conceptualized

- Translator
 - Nested-to-nested-structure
 - Class hierarchy
 - Individual assignment

Dictionary key	MeanderElement4
Super-class prefLabel in ontology	CfdSimulations
Class prefLabel in ontology	MeanderElement

[1] <https://www.vimmp.eu/>
[2] <https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO>

Process Steps

- Segmentation
 - Divided into concepts
 - Comparability
 - Reuses/reduces data

Segmentation hierarchy list example

Named:	'FLOW'
Named:	'DOMAIN'
Named:	'BOUNDARY'
Non-named:	'BOUNDARY CONDITIONS'

Process Steps

- Segmentation
 - Divided into concepts
 - Comparability
 - Reuses/reduces data

- Population [1,2]
 - Automation
 - Adaptable

[1] Lamy, Jean-Baptiste (2017), owlready2-python-package
 [2] EMMOntopy-python package, <https://emmo-repo.github.io/EMMO-python/1.0.1>

- Inferred classification vs preclassification
 - Inferring does not cluster (chaotic)
 - Preclassification is structured (methodical)
 - Clustering into human-interpretable concepts

Metrics / Program Performance

- Code stable
 - Test set: 128 simulations
 - Validation set: 783 simulations
- Population code
 - Optimizable
 - Optimization by inventory
 - Benchmarking and cross verification
 - Data condensation
 - Reducing pseudo duplicates
 - Extending instead of reconstruction

Program	Performance for 911 Simulations	
Data Extraction	69s	8.8M Lines
Segmentation	7min 03s	615 Segments of 36 Concepts
Population	14min 44s	

Performed with 8GB RAM and Intel i5-7200U CPU

Ontology	EMMO *	EMMO * + 911 Simulations	
Classes	470	846	Δ 376
Object Prop.	47	464	Δ 417
Data Prop.	3	258	Δ 255
Individuals	1	4,894	Δ 4893
Axioms	3,363	528,931	Δ 525,568

* Currently only EMMO_1.0.0_beta_0 inferred in 6min 52s


```

1 PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
2 PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
3 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
4 PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#>
5 PREFIX skos: <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>
6 PREFIX emmo: <http://emmo.info/emmo#>
7
8 SELECT ?SimPrefL ?Boundary ?indivPrefL ?Value
9
10 WHERE { ?indivCls skos:prefLabel ?IndivClsPrefL.
11 ?individual a ?indivCls.
12 ?individual skos:prefLabel ?indivPrefL.
13 ?individual emmo:hasSimulation ?Sim.
14 ?Sim skos:prefLabel ?SimPrefL.
15 ?Sim emmo:hasUmomKpiMinConv ?Value.
16 ?Boundary emmo:hasDefIndividual ?individual.
17 ?BoundaryTyp emmo:hasIndividual ?Boundary.
18 ?BoundaryTyp emmo:hasBoundaryType ?Typ.
19
20 FILTER (STR(?IndivClsPrefL) = "BoundaryComponentIndividual")
21 FILTER (?Value <0.95)
22 FILTER (STR(?Typ)="INLET")
23 }
    
```

Simulation Name	Boundary Name	Component Name	Convergence KPI
Mesh_independence_study_Mesh1_Mesh1_files_dp0_CFX_i_CFXFluid_Flow_CFX_006	FlowAnalysis1_DefaultDomain_Inlet_0	FlowAnalysis1_DefaultDomain_Inlet_Water_0	0.9489
	FlowAnalysis1_DefaultDomain_Inlet_1		
Hydrodynamics_Type_5_Hydrodynamics_Type_5	FlowAnalysis1_DefaultDomain_Inlet_0	FlowAnalysis1_DefaultDomain_Inlet_0	0.9396

Process Steps - Summary

- FAIR data access by FAIR data storage
- Dictionary-to-ontology
 - Nested-to-nested
 - Unknown/varying structure
- Ontology
 - Knowledge graph
 - Classifiers due to segments
- Validated

Outlook

- Connection to database
 - Ontology extension instead of recreation
 - Connect Knowledge Graph to database

- From Excel- to RDF-translator
 - Creating complex relations swiftly
 - Decoupling ontology creating from data population

- Usecases outside of database
 - Reperforming simulation with minimal dataset (RDF, mesh, additional inputs)

	M	0.03	M	0.06	M	0.09	M	1	M	3	M	4
0	0.102	0.083	0.077	0.064	0.066	0.068						
1	0.227	0.166	0.144	0.111	0.174	0.215						
2	0.320	0.223	0.188	0.141	0.252	0.342						
3	0.403	0.274	0.226	0.168	0.320	0.460						
4	0.478	0.321	0.261	0.194	0.384	0.560						
5	0.546	0.365	0.295	0.218	0.443	0.636						
6	0.605	0.408	0.327	0.242	0.500	0.696						

Questions?

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